

Shifting Cultivation to Settled Agriculture : Agrarian Change and Tribal Development in Mizoram

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Abstract

Shifting Cultivation has been one of the main livelihood options for many a tribe in India from time immemorial. It is widely practiced in the hill region of the North Eastern states. Although practiced widely it has been construed as one of the major challenges to tribal development in India over many decades. Hence, respective state governments have implemented a number of programmes to wean people away from the ecologically destructive practice of shifting cultivation. Yet one major question that remains unanswered is how far has the switchover from shifting to settled cultivation improved their living conditions? Another closely related question is regarding the nature of change in the tribal agrarian structure in the wake of the switch to settled cultivation. The present paper addresses these research questions with the help of field a survey using a pre-tested structured household interview schedule in two Mizo villages in Mizoram.

Keywords: *Shifting Cultivation, Settled Agriculture, Jhum, Tribal Development, Agrarian Transformation, Agrarian Change*

Introduction

The present paper attempts to assess the impact of agrarian change from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture on the tribal living conditions in Mizoram. Shifting cultivation has been viewed as one of the challenges to tribal development in India over many decades (Zaitinwavra and Kanagaraj, 2008). Shifting cultivation is an agricultural system characterised by rotation of field rather than of crops by short period of cropping alternating with long fallow periods and by means of slash and burn (Sachidananda, 1989). Its

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other features are clearing by means of fire, absence of drought animals and manuring, use of human labour only, employment of dibbling stick or hoe, short periods of soil occupancy alternating with fallow periods.

Tribal communities and hill people have practiced shifting cultivation in India from time immemorial. It is widely practiced in the hilly regions of the North Eastern states of Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland and Tripura. About 10 million hectares of tribal land stretched across 16 states is estimated to be under shifting cultivation (Eswaraiah, 2003). According to a recent estimate of Forest Survey of India based on satellite images, 1.73 million hectares of land is affected by shifting cultivation in the Northeast India, while an estimated 12 per cent of tribal population in India still practices shifting cultivation, the number of families involved in shifting cultivation is estimated to be 4.5 lakhs (Darlong, 2004)

Shifting cultivation is accepted as an early stage of agricultural evolution which is still practiced in different parts of the world across different cultures (Rolwey-Conway, 1984). Shifting Cultivation is not only practiced in India but it is widely prevalent among the indigenous communities, particularly in Africa, Latin America and also parts of Asia.

In spite of its pivotal role in the culture and livelihood of tribal societies, shifting cultivation is often perceived as threat to the forest ecological system and the environment as a whole. As shifting cultivation is always attended by clearing and burning of forests which destroys forest and damages the environment around us. This practice has been criticised by environmentalists, foresters, development practitioners and policy makers as policy makers as being primitive, backward, destructive, or wasteful (Zaitinwawra and Kanagaraj, 2008).

The government and some other initiatives try to protect environment and forests resources by rejecting and opposing the practice of shifting cultivation. But as there was no alternative to jhuming for livelihood, even which the government could not prevent this practice initially. So, shifting cultivation as declared by the government is the main reason for destruction of the forest ecology.

Agrarian structure and change have been fertile areas of social science research in India. Economists, sociologists and historians have

conducted a number of studies on these aspects of social structure (Athreya et al, 1990; Harris, 1982; Mukerjee, 1949; Shah, 2013; Gadgil et al, 1983; Thorner, 1968) in various agro climatic zones of India. There are studies on the changes in the agrarian structure and its impact on rural development (Harris, 1982; GOI, 2007). There are studies which focus on the agrarian reforms (Joshi, 1969) and agricultural technology (Brass, 1990; Basant, 1987; Byres, 1981) and their impact on the agrarian structure as well as rural living conditions.

As agriculture is the main source of livelihood for most of the tribes, there are a number of studies on tribal agriculture in India. In this area, studies have concentrated on the agrarian structure and change, as well as crucial agrarian issues of shifting cultivation and land alienation (Saravanan, 2001; Karuppaiyan, 1990a). On shifting cultivation too there is copious literature in India as many tribes depend upon that for their sustenance. The studies generally focus on social and economic aspects shifting cultivation in different contexts such as jhum cycle, ecological consequences, cropping pattern, input use (Sachidananda, 1989), willingness to switchover to settled agriculture (Zaitinwara and Kanagaraj, 2008) etc.

There are also studies on the tribal development, especially the living conditions and the livelihood of the tribal households in different areas (Ramachandran, 2012; Rajarathnam and Guruswami, 1987; Karupaiyan, 1990b; Manivannan, 1989). Some have attempted to study inter-tribal variations in tribal development (Kanagaraj, 2014).

From the overview of literature it could be observed that there are a number of studies which have been conducted in varied agrarian and tribal contexts. Social scientists, especially the economists, sociologists, anthropologists, historians, etc., have explored the agrarian question from different disciplinary angles, varied theoretical perspectives and methodological orientations. Among the theoretical approaches, political economy is predominant while the quantitative approach is the methodological orientation that is prominent. In spite of these, a few research gaps could be observed.

Firstly, there are a few empirical studies on this problem in Mizoram (see Zaitinwara and Kanagaraj, 2008). Even this study has

confined itself to one village in the vicinity of Aizawl town. The findings of this study may not be reflecting the real situation in Mizoram.

Secondly, a few studies focus on impact of the switchover from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture on the agrarian structure (Zaitinavwra and Kanagaraj, 2008; Ninan, 1992). Even these studies could not demonstrate clearly the effect of agrarian change on the tribal development as they did not operationalise the concept of tribal development.

Thirdly, social workers have not adequately researched on tribal development, i.e., tribal livelihood (Zaitinavwra and Kanagaraj, 2008) or living conditions (Kanagaraj, 2005). The present study tries to fill these gap by comparison of living conditions of the shifting cultivators and settled agriculturalists.

This study is policy oriented and its findings would be useful for policy makers, planners, civil society organizations as well as social workers at multilevel who are concerned with tribal welfare in the North-East. The results will show the directions for designing appropriate policies for promoting sustainable agriculture in the North-East. It will also benefit civil society organisations to develop advocacy strategies. Social workers at the micro, mezzo and macro levels will be able design appropriate intervention strategies for promoting tribal development and empowerment.

The present paper is presented in five sections. The first section presents an over view of shifting cultivation in Mizoram. In the second section the research problem and methodology are presented. In the third section a brief description of the study village is presented. The results and discussion are presented in the fourth section. In the last section concluding observations and suggestions for policy makers is presented.

Shifting Cultivation in Mizoram: An Overview

Mizos have been agriculturists from the beginning of the 18th century when they made their western trek to the Mizo hills. They know only the form of farming known as shifting cultivation which forms the major activity of Mizo economic life even today. Wet rice cultivation is reported to have been first practiced in the year 1921 by the Mizo residents of Burma, which marked the recorded adoption of a new technology in the culture of rice farming among the ethnic group of the Mizo (Thangchungnunga, 1997).

The culture of the Mizos is intrinsically woven with their practice of shifting cultivation. The important festivals of Mizos, viz., Chapchar Kut, Pawl Kut and Mim Kut, are in fact associated with the various stages of shifting cultivation (Sen, 1992).

In Mizoram, the livelihood base of a majority of the population is cultivation, especially shifting cultivation. In the state, 61 per cent of the working population depends on agriculture and of which nearly 55 per cent were cultivators and 6 per cent were agricultural labourers according to the 2001 census. According to the statistical abstract of Department of Agriculture and Minor Irrigation, Government of Mizoram (2004), out of 738 villages and 1,54,643 households, 89,454 (57.85%) are cultivator households in Mizoram. Among the cultivators 78,195 (87%) households are practicing jhum and wet rice cultivation is practiced by 11,301 households (13%) (Zaitinvawra and Kanagaraj, 2008).

A predominant majority of the households are depending on shifting cultivation for their livelihood over all the districts of Mizoram except Aizawl. Of the 1, 54,643 households in the state, more than one half depend on shifting cultivation (60%). More than three-fourth of the households of the districts of Champhai (77%), Kolasib (77%) and Saiha (75%) are shifting cultivators. Likewise, more than two-thirds of the households of Mamit (68%) and Serchip (68%) are practicing shifting cultivation and one half of them in the districts of Lawngtlai (62%) and Lunglei (58%) are jhumias. On the other hand, over one-third of the households of the Aizawl (34%) district depend on shifting cultivation (GOM, 2004).

As regards the agrarian structure of Mizoram, a predominant majority of the cultivators are marginal farmers cultivating less than one hectare of land. Seventy per cent of the cultivators are marginal farmers (less than 1 Hectare), 20 per cent of them are small farmers, while medium and large farmers constitute 6 and 4 per cent. The mean size of land holding was worked out to 1.6 hectares (Zaitinvawra and Kanagaraj, 2008).

A notable feature of the agrarian structure in Mizoram is that inequality is emerging in what otherwise was known as an egalitarian tribal society. Seventy per cent of the marginal farmers are in possession of 21 percent of land, while 10 per cent of medium

and large farmers control over 60 per cent of land (Zaitinwawra and Kanagaraj, 2008).

Research Problem

The present study focuses on the impact of agrarian change, i.e., the switchover from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture on tribal development in Mizoram from a social policy and social work perspective. Agrarian structure is probed in terms of the nature of land ownership and distribution of land across size of land holding classes. Further, the changing patterns of cropping, tools, and implement and input use were also probed into. Tribal development is probed in terms of indicators of living conditions of the tribal households such as annual household income, annual household expenditure and household saving, and investments and their patterns.

Methodology

This study is cross sectional in nature and descriptive in design. It is mainly based on the primary data collected through a pretested structured household interview schedule in two sample villages. In addition, participatory methods, viz., timeline, social map, and seasonal diagram were used to understand the social and ecological context of sample villages and cultivation practices.

The study adopted a multistage sampling procedure to select districts, blocks, villages and households. The study was conducted in Aizawl and Kolasib districts. They were purposively selected in view of the fact that they constitute a majority of the rural households in Mizoram. In Aizawl district, one representative village predominantly occupied by settled agriculturists were chosen. And in Kolasib district, one representative village predominantly relying on shifting cultivation was also chosen purposively. In each of the villages, the lists of very poor, poor and non-poor households were collected from the village council presidents. In each of the categories, using systematic random sampling, households were proportionately selected.

The quantitative data collected through the field survey was processed with computer packages of MS excel and SPSS. To analyse the data, cross tabulation, simple averages, percentages, ratios and

proportions were used. Apart from them 't' test and Karl Pearson's Product moment correlation were used to draw inferences.

The Setting : Profile of Study Villages

For profiling the village communities, key informant interviews and participatory research methods as well as available secondary data with the village council were mainly used. Key informants interviews at tea stalls and Bazars were conducted to have a better understanding of the two communities and agricultural practices. Participatory research methods of social map and seasonal calendar were used to understand the spatial and temporal features of the two villages. Social Mapping exercise was conducted in the two villages at Lungdai and Sesawng. The village elders and leaders of the community based organisations were the participants. The map was prepared by the local people on 7th June 2010 at Lungdai, which is a settled agricultural village, and on 14th June 2010 at Sesawng, which is shifting cultivators' village. The members were 13 members at Sesawng and 12 members at Lungdai. Different age groups from adults to elderly, both men and women, provided rich information. Seasonal diagrams of two villages were also prepared by the key informants. They were prepared by the local people on 7th June 2010 at Lungdai and on 14th June 2010 at Sesawng. The original table was written in the Mizo language which was translated into English.

Lungdai: A Settled Agriculturists Village

Lungdai Village is part of Kolasib District. It was established in 1908. It is located 30 km north of Aizawl. The proportion of female population was almost the same as male. In this village a few denominations were professed, of which the Presbyterian Church is the main denomination.

We could observe the households' access to government services in the community indicating that people in community have higher access to the government services and banking system. But there was no educational institution above the matriculation level which contributes to the lower educational status of its people.

This community could be called a settled agriculture village and only a few migrants from Manipur are practicing shifting

cultivation. Most of the lands were under Land Settlement Certificate and Periodic land pass from the village council. Squash was the main crop cultivated in the village for which the community was well known in Aizawl. Most of the cultivation and crops were commercialised (See figure1).

Sesawng: The Shifting Cultivators' Village

Sesawng is an old village where Mizos have lived for many generations. It is a place where Lalburha, one of the famous Mizo chiefs along with other seven village chiefs, mobilised people to oppose the invasion of the British. As it is 48 km away north of the heart of Aizawl, the capital of Mizoram, less access to government services was observed (See figure2).

It is a traditional village where most of the villagers depend on shifting cultivation for their subsistence. Although some few semi-settled cultivators were observed, most of them failed because of the lack of irrigation. Shifting cultivation is still widely practiced, while a few people practice settled agriculture and grow crops like banana. Most of the lands near the settlement were owned by the rich people from Aizawl.

Results and Discussion

In the previous section, the profiles of the villages were presented. In this light, this section presents the discussion of the results of analysis of quantitative data collected through the field survey. This section is presented in terms of three broad sections, viz., patterns of agrarian structure, tribal development and pattern of relationship between agrarian structure and tribal development.

i. Patterns of Agrarian Structure

To understand the changes in the agrarian structure, three sets of indicators, viz., pattern of land possessed, cropping pattern, and livestock ownership, were analysed and the results are discussed in this section.

Patterns of Land Possessed

The first indicator of agrarian change studied is the of land possession which is analysed for variation in pattern of distribution across

various types of land possession and among the size of land holding classes. Four types of land possession could be observed in context of Mizoram which form a continuum of community ownership to complete private ownership. They are Common Land, Temporary Pass (VC Pass), Periodic Land Pass (PLP), and Land Settlement Certificate (LSC is equivalent to *Patta* land) (Zaitinwawra and Kanagaraj 2008).

The results indicate that the cultivators in the settled villages have predominantly switched over to settled cultivation from shifting cultivation, while those in the other village were practicing shifting cultivation (See table 1). Most of the lands possessed by settled cultivators are under LSC (64%) and some are still under PLP (26%). On the other hand, most of the lands possessed by shifting cultivators are under common land (76%).

As a result of the switchover from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture, the area of land possessed on an average by a household has slightly increased, but significantly. The mean size of total land holding among shifting cultivators worked out to be 3.5 acres while it was 2.9 acres in the case of settled cultivators. This difference was statistically significant. Similarly, the area of land under LSC, and PLP were slightly greater in case of settled cultivators as compared to shifting cultivators. On the other hand, the area under common ownership was greater in the case of shifting cultivators as compared to settled cultivators. While in the area under VC pass, no significant difference could be observed.

Size of Land Holding

Distribution of households across the size of land holding classes is another indicator taken for understanding the changes in the land possession. The size of land holding is categorised into three classes such as marginal (Below 2 acres), Small (2-5 Acres), and Medium (5-10 Acres).

The results indicate that there is significant difference in the pattern of land distribution between settled and shifting cultivator villages. As a result of the switch over from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture there is embourgeoisement in the agrarian structure. Most of the shifting cultivators are marginal farmers (53%) while most of the settled agriculturalists were small farmers (54%).

The proportion of small farmers and medium farmers is greater among the settled cultivators as compared to shifting cultivators. On the other hand, the proportion of marginal farmers is greater among the shifting cultivators as compared to settled cultivators. The size of land possessed by the settled agriculturalists (3.4 Acres) is significantly greater than that of the shifting cultivators (2.94 Acres). The mean land holding size is significantly greater among the settled agriculturalists (See table 2).

Interestingly, the switchover from shifting cultivation resulted in embourgeoisement but has not resulted in emergence of large or very large farmers. There was not a single large farmer found in both the villages. But our discussion with the key informants indicated that some rich people from Aizawl city own large areas of land in this village which shows emergence of absentee land ownership.

Cropping Pattern

Cropping pattern is the second set of indicators chosen for assessing the nature of agrarian change. Crops cultivated were classified into seven types, viz., Cereals, Pulses, Oilseeds, Vegetables, Fruit, Trees, and Other Commercial crops as in an earlier study in Mizoram by Zaitinwara and Kanagaraj (2008).

The number of crops and area under different crops were the two indicators analysed to understand the changes in the cropping pattern. The results indicate that the switchover from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture resulted in mono-cropping and commercialisation of cropping pattern.

Diversification of crops was found in the cropping pattern among the shifting cultivators and they predominantly cultivate for self-consumption. On the other hand, the settled cultivators cultivate the marketable vegetables and commercial crops in a mono cropping pattern. On the average, shifting cultivators cultivate 7 crops while settled cultivators grow only three crops in a year. The number of cereals and vegetables cultivated by shifting cultivators on an average is greater as compared to settled cultivators. On the contrary, the settled cultivators grow more of oil seeds, fruits, tree crops, and other commercial crops. Interestingly, the settled cultivators grow no cereals like rice while the shifting cultivators cultivate no commercial or tree crops (See table 3).

The indicator area under cultivation also reveals a similar picture of cropping pattern. Most of the area under settled agriculture is used for cultivating vegetables while that of shifting cultivators was under cereals. The main crop is Squash. As the settled agriculturalist move from diversification of crops to mono cropping, they started to look after only one or two crops concentrating their effort and skills to increase production. The settled agriculturalist grow more commercial crops such as coffee, *Zawngtah*, *Hmunphiah*, etc., than cereals and the area used for this was also larger than for other crops. The shifting cultivators do not grow any commercial crops in particular, but they consume most of their products and also sell the surplus.

In the cropping pattern, two main shifts were observed. While moving from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture the patterns of cropping moved from crop diversity to mono cropping and also from subsistence to commercialisation of crops (See table 3).

Patterns of Livestock Ownership

Livestock rearing is one of the sources of livelihood in tribal communities from time immemorial. In the context of Mizoram, it was customary for the Mizos to rear only pigs and cow rearing was unknown. In this subsection, the differential patterns of livestock ownership between the shifting cultivators and settled agriculturists is analysed and discussed. The livestock owned among the shifting and settled agriculturalist were of four types, viz., Pig, Goat, Poultry Bird and Cow (See table 4).

The settled agriculturalists, on an average, reared more number of livestock than the shifting cultivators. Moreover, the value of livestock held by households on an average was greater among the settled cultivators (Rs 38,014) as compared to that of shifting cultivators (Rs 8,075). The settled cultivation and livestock rearing are interdependent as the by-products of cultivation are used as fodder for the livestock and in turn livestock especially the cows help in weeding and they also supply organic manure for the cultivation of the commercial crops. The total value of livestock owned by the households is significantly greater among the settled cultivators (Rs 38,014) as compared to shifting cultivators (Rs 8,075).

Pigs constitute the predominant form of livestock owned by both settled cultivators and shifting cultivators. However, the value of pigs owned is greater among the settled agriculturalists (Rs 21,576) than that of shifting cultivators (Rs 7,640). Yet the share of the value of pigs in the total value of livestock is greater among the shifting cultivators (95%) as compared to the settled cultivators (57%).

Cow rearing which was unknown in traditional Mizo society has emerged among the settled cultivators, while none among the shifting cultivators rear cows. The mean value of the cows owned by the settled agriculturalists was worked out to Rs 16,110 which constitutes 42 per cent of the share of total value of livestock owned by them.

For some of the settled agriculturalists, livestock rearing has become the main occupation and cultivation has become secondary. This clearly shows that moving from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture results in the diversification of occupation.

ii. Tribal Development: Living Conditions

To assess the tribal development, the pattern and level of Annual Household Income, Annual Household Expenditure, Households' Savings and Debt as well as Housing were analysed.

Household Income

Household Income is the first indicator of standard of living. It is analysed in terms of source pattern and level. Agriculture, Government Service, Business, Agriculture labour and Livestock Rearing constitute the sources of income in the study area (See table 5). The results of analysis of pattern of annual income clearly demonstrate that switchover from shifting cultivation to settled-agriculture has resulted in diversification of income for Mizo households. The main source of household income among the shifting cultivators was Agriculture (67%), while among the settled agriculturalists the main sources of income were Livestock Rearing (39%) and Agriculture (36%).

The analysis of actual income source-wise between the shifting cultivators and settled agriculturalists reveal that the settled cultivators have greater household income as compared to the shifting cultivators

from all the sources except agricultural labour. Total average annual household income of the settled cultivators (Rs 106,874) was significantly higher than that of the settled cultivators (Rs 40,859). Likewise, the mean annual household income from agriculture was significantly greater among the settled cultivators (Rs 38,860) as compared to those of shifting cultivators (Rs 27,540). Similarly, income from government service, business and livestock rearing were significantly greater for the settled cultivators as compared to the shifting cultivator households.

Household Expenditure

The second indicator of standard of living is annual household expenditure. The differences in the pattern and level of household expenditure between shifting cultivators and settled agriculturists are discussed here. Annual household expenditure is classified as food and non-food components (See table 6). The major share of annual household expenditure was incurred on food in the case of settled cultivators (61%) while most part of the expenditure of the shifting cultivators was spent on non-food items (55%). This is contrary to the prediction of Engel's law according to which as income of household increases, the proportion of income spent on food declines, even though the actual expenditure on food increases. This could be attributed to the fact that the shifting cultivators undervalue their produce used for their own consumption.

In spite of that, the annual household expenditure of the settled cultivators (Rs 4,930) was significantly greater as compared to shifting cultivators (Rs 2,249). On both the components of household expenditure, viz., food and non-food, the settled agriculturists on an average incur greater expenditure as compared to the shifting cultivator households.

Household Savings and Debt

The patterns and levels of household savings and debt, which constitute the third set of indicators of living conditions, are discussed here (See table 7). The results of analyses on the pattern of saving and investment as well as debt clearly demonstrate that there is a greater degree of financial inclusion among the settled cultivators as compared to the shifting cultivator households. Among the settled

cultivators, most of the household savings were in the form of deposits in the Commercial banks (99%) while savings of the shifting cultivators were equally divided between cash in hand (45%) and savings in commercial banks(45%). Similarly, most of the debt of the settled agriculturist households was owed to the commercial banks (100%) while most of the loans of the shifting cultivators were borrowed from friends and relatives (67%).

Similar to the levels of income and expenditure, in the levels of household savings and debt also the settled agriculturalists were better off as compared to the shifting cultivators. The total household savings of the settled cultivators (Rs 62,232) was far greater as compared to that of shifting cultivators (Rs 5,448). Similarly, though meagre in quantity, the household debt of the settled cultivators (Rs 4,600) was higher as compared to that of the shifting cultivators (Rs 121).

Housing and Amenities

Housing and amenities constitute the last set of indicators analysed to gauge the differences in the living conditions of the settled and shifting cultivators. They are ownership of house, electricity, toilet with septic tank, phone/mobile, water connection, gas connection, and vehicle (two or four wheeler). In almost all of these indicators the greater proportion of settled cultivators had possession of them (See table 8). Though a majority of the households of shifting cultivators own houses, have electricity, toilet with septic tank, phone and gas connection, the proportion of the settled cultivators possessing them is greater. The housing and amenities index which is a composite of proportion of all these indicators is also significantly greater for settled cultivators (0.73) as compared to shifting cultivators (0.56). Interestingly, about 73 per cent of the settled cultivators have access to all these facilities or amenities while only 56 per cent of the shifting cultivators have all of these.

iii. Relationship between Agrarian Structure and Tribal Development

The comparison of shifting cultivators and settled agriculturists demonstrated that the agrarian change has contributed to farm diversification and increase in the income. To further identify the specific aspect of agrarian structure that contributes to tribal

development, i.e. improvement in the living conditions the Karl Pearson's Coefficients of correlation were used. Apart from elements of agrarian structure such as area under Land Settlement Certificate area under Periodic Land Pass, area under Temporary Pass (VC), area under Common Land and Size of Landholding, also Gross Cropped Area, Number of Crops Cultivated and Value of Livestock were assessed for correlation with the indicators of living conditions such as Annual Household Income, Annual Household Expenditure, Total Household Saving, Total Household Debt, Housing and Amenities Index (See table 9).

The results of correlation analysis clearly reveal that the switchover from shifting cultivation to settled cultivation results in improvement in the tribal living conditions and contributes to tribal development. Among the indicators of change in agrarian structure, viz., Area under Land Settlement Certificate, Periodic Land Pass, and size of land holding have significant positive relationship with most of the indicators of tribal development viz., Annual Household Income, Household Expenditure, total Household Saving, total Household Debt, and Housing & Amenities Index. On the other hand, the area under common land has significant positive relationship with most of the indicators of tribal development(see table 9).

A probe further into the relationship between the indicators of change in cropping reveals that as the gross cropping area increased, the living conditions have improved. Further, the switch over from multi cropping to mono cropping has also resulted in improvement in the living conditions of tribal households. There were significant positive relationship between gross cropped area and annual household expenditure, total household saving, and housing and amenities index. On the other hand, there is a significant negative relationship between number of crops cultivated by the farmer households and their living conditions in terms of increase in annual household expenditure, household savings, and housing and amenities (see table 9).

The correlation analysis also indicates that livestock rearing, which emerged with the switchover to settled cultivation, has contributed to improved living conditions of the households. The relationship between value of livestock and all the indicators of living condition, viz, annual household income, annual household

expenditure, household saving, household debt and household amenities index are positive and significant(see table 9).

Conclusion

The study clearly shows that the switchover from shifting cultivation to settled cultivation results in improvement in the living conditions in Mizoram. The switchover to settled cultivation has also resulted in commercialisation and emergence of mono cropping with a single vegetable crop. Further, the improvement in living conditions was not only due to commercialisation in cropping pattern but also because of farm diversification, especially the emergence of livestock rearing which was not popular among the Mizos in the past and even today in other parts of the state. One disturbing finding is that though the income from agriculture has increased, it is not too great. Another problem is that the mono cropping pattern that emerged in the wake of settlement. In case of failure of perishable crops such as squash whether the income of cultivators will be sustainable? Further, if all over Mizoram such switchover to settled cultivation and mono cropping happens, whether there will be adequate markets for all the produce. The implication of the study is that while promoting settled cultivation, the government needs take adequate measures to promote crop diversification, farm diversification as well as better transportation and markets for the agricultural produce. It also needs to restrict allotment of land to those who live in the particular village rather than to the rich people from other areas.

References

- Athreya, V. Djurfeld, G. Lindberg, (1990), Barriers Broken : Production Relation and Agrarian Change, *Social Scientist*, 14(5), 3-14.
- Basant, R. (1987), Agriculture Technology and Employment in India : A Survey of Recent Research, *Economic and Political Weekly*, 22(32), 1348-1364.
- Brass, T. (1990), Class Struggle and the Deproletarianisation of Agriculture Labour in Haryana (India), *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 18(1), 36-67.

- Byres, T. (1981), The New Technology, Class Formation, Class Action in the Indian Countryside, *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 8(4), 405-454.
- Darlong, V. T. (2004), *To Jhum or not to Jhum : Policy Perspective on Shifting Cultivation*, Guwahati : The Missing Link.
- Eswaraiah, G. (2003), Challenges of Rural Eco System in India, *Employment News*, 27(50), 1-3.
- Gadgil, M. N. Prasad, N. and Ali, R. (1983), Forest Management in India : A Critical Review, *Social Action*, 33(2), 127-155.
- Government of India, (2007), *Tenth Five Year Plan*, New Delhi : Planning Commission.
- Government of Mizoram, (2004), *Statistical Hand Book*, Aizawl : Department of Economic and Statistics.
- Harris, J. (1982), *Capitalism and Peasant Farming : Agrarian Structure and Ideology in Northern Tamil Nadu*, Bombay : Oxford University Press.
- Joshi, P. C. (1969), Agrarian Social Structure and Social Change, *Sankhyā: The Indian Journal of Statistics*, Series B, 31(3/4), 479-490.
- Kanagaraj, E. (2005), Human Development and Social Exclusion of Scheduled Tribes in Tamil Nadu, *Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation*, Annamalai Nagar : Annamalai University.
- Kanagaraj, E. (2014), *Human Development and Social Exclusion among Primitive Tribes in India*, Deutschland / Germany : Lambert Academic Publishing.
- Karuppaiyan, E. (1990), Alienation of Tribal Lands in Tamil Nadu. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 25 (22), 1185-1186.
- Manivannan, S. (1989), A Study of Tribal Poverty and Indebtedness with Special Reference to Malayali Tribe of South Arcot Karayan Hills, Tamil Nadu. *Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis*, Annamalai Nagar : Anamalai University.
- Mukherjee, R. (1949), The Economic Structure and Social Life in Six Villages of Bengal, *American Sociological Review*, 14(3), 415-425.
- Ninan, K.N. (1992), Economics of Shifting Cultivation in India, *Economic and Political Weekly*, 27 (13), 67-91.
- Rajarathnam, T. N. and Guruswami, P. A. (1987), *Taking Technology to Tribal People and Communities : Report of the Phase I (Survey) of the Project*, Coimbatore: Sri Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya Arts College.
- Ramachandran, S. (2012), *Tribal Development Programmes in India*, New Delhi: Abhijeet Publications.
- Rolwey-Conway, (1984), Slash and Burn in the Temperate European

- Neolithic. In R. Mercer (Ed), *Farming Practice in the British Prehistory*, Edinburgh : Edinburgh University Press.
- Sachidananda, (1989), *Shifting Cultivation in India*, New Delhi : Concept Publishing Company.
- Saravanan, V. (2001), Tribal Land Alienation in Madras Presidency during the Colonial Period, 1792-1947, *Review of Development and Change*, 6(1), 73-104.
- Sen, S. (1992), Tribes of Mizoram : Description Ethnology and Bibliography, New Delhi : Gian Publishing House.
- Shah, A. (2013), The Agrarian Question in a Maoist Guerrilla Zone : Land, Labour and Capital in the Forests and Hills of Jharkhand, India, *Journal of Agrarian Change*, 13(3), 424-450.
- Thangchungnunga, (1997), Shifting Cultivation and Emerging Pattern of Change in Land Relation, In L.K. Jha (Ed), *Natural Resource Management Mizoram*, New Delhi: APH Publishing Corporation.
- Thorner, D. (1968), Predatory Capitalism in Indian Agriculture, *Economic and Political Weekly*, 3 (43), A3-A4.
- Zaitinwawra, D. and Kanagaraj, E. (2008), Shifting Cultivation to Settled Agriculture: Rural Livelihood Patterns in Mizoram, *The Eastern Anthropologist*, 61 (2), 201-226.

Table 1 : Patterns of Land Possessed
(Area in Acres)

Sl.No.	Nature of Ownership	Mode of Cultivation						't'
		Settled n = 100		Shifting n = 70		Total N = 170		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	Land Settlement Certificate(LSC)	2.20 (63.62)	2.07	0.21 (7.28)	1.03	1.38 (42.56)	1.97	7.39**
2	Periodic Land Pass(PLP)	0.91 (26.23)	1.75	0.03 (0.97)	0.24	0.54 (16.79)	1.42	4.15**
3	Temporary Pass(VCP)	0.15 (4.35)	0.72	0.47 (16.02)	1.61	0.28 (8.71)	1.18	1.76
4	Common Ownership(CO)	0.20 (5.80)	0.67	2.23 (75.73)	1.35	1.04 (31.94)	1.42	12.93**
5	Total Area of Land Possessed	3.45 (100)	5.20	2.94 (100)	4.24	3.24 (100)	5.99	9.25**

Source : Computed Figures in the parentheses are percentages ** P<0.01 * P<0.05

Table 2 : Size of Land Holding

Sl. No.	Size of Landholding	Mode of Cultivation		Total N = 170
		Settled n = 100	Shifting n = 70	
1	Marginal(Below 2 Acres)	31 (31.00)	37 (52.86)	68 (40.00)
2	Small(2-5 Acres)	54 (54.00)	28 (40.00)	82 (48.24)
3	Medium(5-10 Acres)	15 (15.00)	5 (7.14)	20 (11.76)
	Total	100 (100)	70 (100)	170 (100)
	Mean Size of Landholding	3.45 – 2.14	2.94 – 1.84	3.24 – 2.03

Source : Computed

Figures in the parentheses are percentages

Mean \pm SD**Table 3 : Cropping Pattern**

Sl. No		Mode of Cultivation					
		Settled n = 100		Shifting n = 70		Total N = 170	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
I	No. of Crops Cultivated						
	Cereals	0.11 (3.6)	0.31	0.97 (14.7)	0.17	0.46 (11.0)	0.50

	Pulses	0.00 (0.00)	0.00	0.00 (0.00)	0.00	0.00 (0.00)	0.00
	Oil seeds	0.32 (10.4)	0.58	0.36 (5.4)	0.48	0.34 (7.9)	0.54
	Vegetables	1.52 (49.2)	0.90	5.16 (77.8)	1.07	3.02 (71.3)	2.04
	Fruits	0.37 (12.0)	0.77	0.14 (2.2)	0.60	0.28 (6.5)	0.71
	Tree Crops	0.24 (7.8)	0.67	0.00 (0.00)	0.00	0.14 (3.3)	0.53
	Other Commercial Crops	0.53 (17.2)	0.56	0 (0.00)	0	0.31 (7.4)	0.50
	Total	3.09 (100)	3.25	6.63 (100)	2.32	4.24 (100)	4.32
II	Area Under Cultivation						
	Cereals	0.24 (9.7)	0.77	2.40 (72.3)	1.13	1.13 (39.9)	1.42
	Pulses	0 (0.00)	0	0 (0.00)	0	0 (0.00)	0
	Oil Seeds	0.27 (10.7)	0.50	0.26 (8.0)	0.39	0.26 (9.4)	0.46
	Vegetables	1.58 (63.4)	0.98	0.61 (18.3)	0.25	1.18 (41.6)	0.90
	Fruits	0.28 (11.1)	0.62	0.05 (1.5)	0.21	0.18 (6.4)	0.51
	Trees	0.13 (5.2)	0.39	0.00 (0.00)	0.00	0.08 (2.7)	0.31

	Other Commercial Crops	0.91 (36.4)	1.26	0 (0.00)	0	0.53 (18.8)	1.06
	Gross Cropped Area	2.49 (100)	3.26	3.32 (100)	1.99	2.83 (100)	3.59
	t'	1.6					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.1					

Source: Computed
 Figures in the parentheses are percentages
 Mean \pm SD

Table 4 : Patterns of Livestock Ownership

Sl. No.	Livestock	Mode of Cultivation					
		Settled n = 100		Shifting n = 70		Total N = 170	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	Pigs	21576 (56.8)	33061.97	7640 (94.6)	19348.09	15837.65 (61.7)	28991.25
2	Goat	0 (0.0)	0	28.57143 (0.4)	239.0457	11.76471 (0.0)	153.393
3	Poultry Birds	328 (0.9)	1688.887	407 (5.0)	726.8761	360.5294 (1.4)	1374.094
4	Cow	16110 (42)	46459.69	0 (0.0)	0	9476.471 (37)	36437.38
5	Total	38014 (100)	81210.54	8075.571 (100)	20314.01	25686.41 (100)	66956.12

Source : Computed
 Figures in the parentheses are percentages

Table 5 : Patterns of Annual Households Income

Sl. No	Source	Mode of Cultivation						t'
		Settled n = 100		Shifting n = 70		Total N = 170		
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
1	Agriculture	38860 (36.36)	30063	27540 (67.40)	14468	34199 (42.91)	25419	2.92**
2	Government Service	13640 (12.76)	38419	0 (0.00)	0	8024 (10.07)	30166	2.97**
3	Business	4210 (3.94)	14292	171 (0.42)	1434	2547 (3.20)	11157	2.35*
4	Agricultural Labour	8020 (7.50)	15742	11871 (29.05)	17038	9606 (12.05)	16349	1.52
5	Livestock Rearing	42144 (39.43)	105609	1276 (3.12)	3802	25316 (31.77)	83345	3.23**
6	Total Annual Household Income	106874 (100)	110981	40859 (100)	26667	79691 (100)	92560	4.88**

Source: Computed Figures in the parentheses are percentages ** P < 0.01 * P<0.05

Table 6 : Patterns of Annual Household Expenditure

Sl.No	Component	Mode of Cultivation						't'
		Settled n = 100		Shifting n = 70		Total N = 170		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	Food	2994.0 (60.72)	1193.0	1009.3 (44.87)	496.0	2176.8 (56.88)	1376.2	13.14**
2	Non- Food	1936.9 (39.28)	1496.2	1240.0 (55.13)	423.4	1649.9 (43.12)	1225.9	3.79**
3	Annual Household Expenditure	4930.9 (100)	2314.4	2249.3 (100)	639.2	3826.7 (100)	2248.7	9.44**

Source : Computed

Figures in the parentheses are percentages

** P < 0.01 * P<0.05

Table 7 : Patterns of Household Savings and Debt

SLNo	Savings and Investments	Mode of Cultivation					
		Settled n = 100		Shifting n = 70		Total N = 170	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
	Cash in Hand	0.0 (0.00)	0.0	2448.6 (44.9)	3624.5	1008.2 (2.6)	2612.3
	Friend and relatives	0.0 (0.00)	0.0	0.0 (0.00)	0.0	0.0 (0.00)	0.0
	Money Lenders	170.0 (0.3)	1700.0	508.6 (9.3)	3602.0	309.4 (0.8)	2649.2
	Commercial Banks	62062.0 (99.7)	117474.1	2462.9 (45.2)	9893.4	37521.2 (96.6)	94813.1
	Post office	0.0 0.0	0.0	28.6 (0.5)	239.0	11.8 (0.0)	153.4
	Total Household Savings	62232.0 (100)	119174.1	5448.6 (100)	17358.9	38850.6 (100)	100228.1

II	Debt								
	Cash in Hand	0 (0.00)	0	40 (32.94)	197.3741	16.47059 (0.60)	127.6525		
	Friend and relatives	0 (0.00)	0	81.42857 (67.06)	289.5738	33.52941 (1.22)	189.3446		
	Commercial Banks	460 (100)	40262.27	0 (0.00)	0	2705.882 (98.19)	30899.27		
	Total Household Debt	4600 (100)	40262.27	121.4286 (100)	486.9479	2755.882 (100)	31216.27		

Source: Computed

Figures in the parentheses are percentages

Table 8 : Housing and Amenities

Sl.No	Particulars	Mode of Cultivation			‘t’
		Settled n = 100	Shifting n = 70	Total N = 170	
1	Own House	98 (98.00)	57 (81.43)	155 (91.18)	3.89**
2	Electricity	99 (99.00)	63 (90.00)	162 (95.29)	2.77**
3	Toilet with Septic Tank	100 (100.00)	51 (72.86)	151 (88.82)	6.07**
4	Phone/ Mobile	96 (96.00)	55 (78.57)	151 (88.82)	3.66**
5	Water Connection	5 (5.00)	1 (1.43)	6 (3.53)	1.24
6	Gas Connection	95 (95.00)	45 (64.29)	140 (82.35)	5.59**
7	Vehicle	19 (19.00)	4 (5.71)	23 (13.53)	2.52**
	Housing and Amenities Index	0.73 – 0.10	0.56 – 0.19	0.66 – 0.16	7.6**

Source : Computed

Figures in the parentheses are percentages Mean ± SD

** P < 0.01 * P<0.05

Table 9 : Agrarian Structure and Tribal Development : Zero Order Correlation Matrix

N = 170

Sl.No	Agrarian Structure	Tribal Development (Living Conditions)				
		Annual Household Income	Annual Household Expenditure	Total Household Saving	Total Household Debt	Housing and Amenities Index
1	Land Settlement Certificate	0.25**	0.36**	0.21**	0.14	0.35**
2	Periodic Land Pass	0.21**	0.32**	0.18*	0.24**	0.10
3	Temporary Pass(VC)	-0.07	-0.12	-0.08	0.00	0.05
4	Common Land	-0.32**	-0.46**	-0.24**	-0.06	-0.31**
5	Size of Landholding	0.14	0.18*	0.12	0.26**	0.23**
6	Gross Cropped Area	0.07	0.18*	0.25**	-0.03	0.21**
7	No. of Crops Cultivated	-0.32**	-0.34**	-0.24**	-0.05	-0.31**
8	Value of Livestock	0.67**	0.52**	0.34**	0.37**	0.27**

Source : Computed ** P < 0.01 * P<0.05

